

July 2020: TOP Must Read Article in Computer Science & Information Technology Research

**International Journal of Computer Science and
Information Technology (IJCSIT)**

Google Scholar Citation

Cited by [VIEW ALL](#)

	All	Since 2015
Citations	7344	5494
h-index	41	32
i10-index	194	162

ISSN: 0975-3826(online); 0975-4660 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit.html>

DETECTION OF FAKE ACCOUNTS IN INSTAGRAM USING MACHINE LEARNING

Ananya Dey¹, Hamsashree Reddy², Manjistha Dey³ and Niharika Sinha⁴

¹National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli, India

²PES University, Bangalore, India

³RV College of Engineering, Bangalore, India

⁴Manipal Institute of Technology, Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

With the advent of the Internet and social media, while hundreds of people have benefitted from the vast sources of information available, there has been an enormous increase in the rise of cyber-crimes, particularly targeted towards women. According to a 2019 report in the [4] Economics Times, India has witnessed a 457% rise in cybercrime in the five year span between 2011 and 2016. Most speculate that this is due to impact of social media such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter on our daily lives. While these definitely help in creating a sound social network, creation of user accounts in these sites usually needs just an email-id. A real life person can create multiple fake IDs and hence impostors can easily be made. Unlike the real world scenario where multiple rules and regulations are imposed to identify oneself in a unique manner (for example while issuing one's passport or driver's license), in the virtual world of social media, admission does not require any such checks. In this paper, we study the different accounts of Instagram, in particular and try to assess an account as fake or real using Machine Learning techniques namely Logistic Regression and Random Forest Algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Logistic Regression, Random Forest Algorithm, median imputation, Maximum likelihood estimation, k cross validation, overfitting, out of bag data, recall, identity theft, Angler phishing.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N5/11519ijcsit07.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Indira Sen, Anupama Aggarwal, Shiven Mian. 2018. "Worth its Weight in Likes: Towards Detecting Fake Likes on Instagram". In ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management.
- [2] Shalinda Adikari, Kaushik Dutta. 2014. "Identifying Fake Profiles In LinkedIn". In Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems.
- [3] Aleksei Romanov, Alexander Semenov, Oleksiy Mazhelis and Jari Veijalainen. 2017. "Detection of Fake Profiles in Social Media". In 13th International Conference on Web Information Systems and Technologies.
- [4] <https://telecom.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/india-saw-457-rise-in-cybercrime-in-fiveyears-study/67455224>
- [5] Todor Mihaylov, Preslav Nakov. 2016. "Hunting for Troll Comments in News Community Forums". In Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [6] ML-cheatsheet.readthedocs.io. (2019). Logistic Regression — ML Cheatsheet documentation. [Online] Available at: https://ml-cheatsheet.readthedocs.io/en/latest/logistic_regression.html#binarylogistic-regression [Accessed 10 Jun. 2019].
- [7] 3. Schoonjans, F. (2019). ROC curve analysis with MedCalc. [Online] MedCalc. Available at: <https://www.medcalc.org/manual/roc-curves.php> [Accessed 10 Jun. 2019].
- [8] Kietzmann, J.H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I.P., Silvestre, B.S., 2011. Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media. *Bus.Horiz., SPECIAL ISSUE: SOCIAL MEDIA* 54, 241251. doi:10.1016/j.bushor.2011.01.005.
- [9] Krombholz, K., Hobel, H., Huber, M., Weippl, E., 2015. Advanced Social Engineering Attacks. *J Inf SecurAppl* 22, 113–122. doi:10.1016/j.jisa.2014.09.005.

BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING REVIEW AND OPPORTUNITIES

**Manoj Muniswamaiah, Tilak Agerwala and Charles Tappert
Seidenberg School of CSIS, Pace University, White Plains, New York**

ABSTRACT

Big Data is used in decision making process to gain useful insights hidden in the data for business and engineering. At the same time it presents challenges in processing, cloud computing has helped in advancement of big data by providing computational, networking and storage capacity. This paper presents the review, opportunities and challenges of transforming big data using cloud computing resources.

KEYWORDS

Big data; cloud computing; analytics; database; data warehouse

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N4/11419ijcsit04.pdf>

Volume Link: http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Konstantinou, I., Angelou, E., Boumpouka, C., Tsoumakos, D., & Koziris, N. (2011, October). [On the elasticity of nosql databases over cloud management platforms](#). In Proceedings of the 20th ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management (pp. 2385-2388). ACM.
- [2] Labrinidis, Alexandros, and Hosagrahar V. Jagadish. "[Challenges and opportunities with big data](#)." Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment 5.12 (2012): 2032-2033.
- [3] Abadi, D. J. (2009). Data management in the cloud: Limitations and opportunities. IEEE Data Eng. Bull, 32(1), 3-12.
- [4] Luhn, H. P. (1958). A business intelligence system. IBM Journal of Research and Development, 2(4), 314-319
- [5] Sivarajah, Uthayasankar, et al. "[Critical analysis of Big Data challenges and analytical methods](#)." Journal of Business Research 70 (2017): 263-286.
- [6] <https://www.bmc.com/blogs/saas-vs-paas-vs-iaas-whats-the-difference-and-how-to-choose/>
- [7] Kavis, Michael J. Architecting the cloud: design decisions for cloud computing service models (SaaS, PaaS, and IaaS). John Wiley & Sons, 2014.
- [8] https://www.ripublication.com/ijaer17/ijaerv12n17_89.pdf
- [9] Sakr, S. & Gaber, M.M., 2014. Large Scale and big data: Processing and Management Auerbach, ed.
- [10] Ji, Changqing, et al. "Big data processing in cloud computing environments." 2012 12th international symposium on pervasive systems, algorithms and networks. IEEE, 2012.
- [11] Han, J., Haihong, E., Le, G., & Du, J. (2011, October). Survey on nosql database. In Pervasive Computing and Applications (ICPCA), 2011 6th International Conference on (pp. 363-366). IEEE.
- [12] Zhang, L. et al., 2013. Moving big data to the cloud. INFOCOM, 2013 Proceedings IEEE, pp.405-409
- [13] Fernández, Alberto, et al. "[Big Data with Cloud Computing: an insight on the computing environment, MapReduce, and programming frameworks](#)." Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery 4.5 (2014): 380-409.
- [14] http://acme.able.cs.cmu.edu/pubs/uploads/pdf/IoTBD_2016_10.pdf
- [15] Xiaofeng, Meng, and Chi Xiang. "[Big data management: concepts, techniques and challenges \[J\]](#)." Journal of computer research and development 1.98 (2013): 146-169.
- [16] Muniswamaiah, Manoj & Agerwala, Tilak & Tappert, Charles. (2019). [Challenges of Big Data Applications in Cloud Computing](#). 221-232. 10.5121/csit.2019.90918.

SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

Te-Shun Chou

**Department of Technology Systems, East Carolina University, Greenville,
NC, U.S.A.**

ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N6/11619ijcsit04.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

REFERENCES

1. DataLossDB Open Security Foundation. <http://datalossdb.org/statistics>
2. Sophos Security Threat Report 2012. <http://www.sophos.com/>
3. Amazon.com Server Said to Have Been Used in Sony Attack, May 2011. <http://www.bloomberg.com/news/2011-05-13/sony-network-said-to-have-been-invaded-by-hackers-using-amazon-com-server.html>
4. D. Jamil and H. Zaki, “[Security Issues in Cloud Computing and Countermeasures](#),” International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, Vol. 3 No. 4, pp. 2672- 2676, April 2011.
5. K. Zunnurhain and S. Vrbsky, “[Security Attacks and Solutions in Clouds](#),” 2nd IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science, Indianapolis, December 2010.
6. W. A. Jansen, “Cloud Hooks: Security and Privacy Issues in Cloud Computing,” 44th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, pp. 1–10, Koloa, Hawaii, January 2011.
7. T. Roth, “[Breaking Encryptions Using GPU Accelerated Cloud Instances](#),” Black Hat Technical Security Conference, 2011.
8. CERT Coordination Center, Denial of Service. http://www.packetstormsecurity.org/distributed/denial_of_service.html
9. M. Jensen, J. Schwenk, N. Gruschka, and L. L. Iacono, “[On Technical Security Issues in Cloud Computing](#),” IEEE International Conference in Cloud Computing, pp. 109-116, Bangalore, 2009.
10. Thunder in the Cloud: \$6 Cloud-Based Denial-of-Service Attack, August 2010. http://blogs.computerworld.com/16708/thunder_in_the_cloud_6_cloud_based_denial_of_service_attack
11. DDoS Attack Rains Down on Amazon Cloud, October 2009. http://www.theregister.co.uk/2009/10/05/amazon_bitbucket_outage/
12. 2011 CyberSecurity Watch Survey, CERT Coordination Center at Carnegie Mellon University.
13. D. Catteddu and G. Hogben, “[Cloud Computing Benefits, Risks and Recommendations for Information Security](#),” The European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA), November 2009.

14. Insider Threats Related to Cloud Computing, CERT, July 2012. <http://www.cert.org/>
15. Data Breach Trends & Stats, Symantec, 2012. <http://www.indefenseofdata.com/data-breach-trendsstats/>
16. 2012 Has Delivered Her First Giant Data Breach, January 2012. <http://www.infosecisland.com/blogview/19432-2012-Has-Delivered-Her-First-Giant-DataBreach.html>
17. A Few Wrinkles Are Etching Facebook, Other Social Sites, USA Today, 2011. http://www.usatoday.com/printedition/life/20090115/socialnetworking15_st.art.html
18. An Update on LinkedIn Member Passwords Compromised, LinkedIn Blog, June, 2012. <http://blog.linkedin.com/2012/06/06/linkedin-member-passwords-compromised/>
19. Dropbox: Yes, We Were Hacked, August 2012. <http://gigaom.com/cloud/dropbox-yes-we-werehacked/>
20. Web Based Attacks, Symantec White Paper, February 2009.
21. Symantec Internet Security Threat Report, 2011 Trends, Vol. 17, April 2012.
22. P. P. Ramgonda and R. R. Mudholkar, "[Cloud Market Cogitation and Techniques to Averting SQL Injection for University Cloud](#)," International Journal of Computer Technology and Applications, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 1217-1224, January, 2012.
23. A. S. Choudhary and M. L. Dhore, "[CIDT: Detection of Malicious Code Injection Attacks on Web Application](#)," International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 52, No. 2, pp. 19-26, August 2012.
24. Web Application Attack Report For The Second Quarter of 2012. <http://www.firehost.com/company/newsroom/web-application-attack-report-second-quarter-2012>
25. Visitors to Sony PlayStation Website at Risk of Malware Infection, July 2008. <http://www.sophos.com/en-us/press-office/press-releases/2008/07/playstation.aspx>
26. N. Provos, M. A. Rajab, and P. Mavrommatis, "Cybercrime 2.0: When the Cloud Turns Dark," ACM Communications, Vol. 52, No. 4, pp. 42–47, 2009.
27. S. S. Rajan, Cloud Security Series | SQL Injection and SaaS, Cloud Computing Journal, November 2010.

28. Researchers Demo Cloud Security Issue With Amazon AWS Attack, October 2011. http://www.pcworld.idg.com.au/article/405419/researchers_demo_cloud_security_is_sue_amazon_aws_attack/
29. M. McIntosh and P. Austel, "XML Signature Element Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," 2005 workshop on Secure web services, ACM Press, New York, NY, pp. 20–27, 2005.
30. N. Gruschka and L. L. Iacono, "[Vulnerable Cloud: SOAP Message Security Validation Revisited](#)," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, Los Angeles, 2009.
31. A. Tripathi and A. Mishra, "Cloud Computing Security Considerations Interface," 2011 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing, Xi'an, China, September 2011.
32. H. C. Li, P. H. Liang, J. M. Yang, and S. J. Chen, "Analysis on Cloud-Based Security Vulnerability Assessment," IEEE International Conference on E-Business Engineering, pp.490-494, November 2010.
33. Amazon:Hey Spammers, Get Off My Cloud!http://voices.washingtonpost.com/securityfix/2008/07/amazon_hey_spammers_get_off_my.html
34. W. Jansen and T. Grance, "Guidelines on Security and Privacy in Public Cloud Computing," Computer Security Division, Information Technology Laboratory, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Special Publication 800-144, December 2011.
35. Tackling the Insider Threat <http://www.bankinfosecurity.com/blogs.php?postID=140>
36. "Cloud Security Risks and Solutions," White Paper, BalaBit IT Security, July 2010.
37. S. J. Stolfo, M. B. Salem, and A. D. Keromytis, "Fog computing: Mitigating Insider Data Theft Attacks in the Cloud," IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy Workshops, pp. 125-128, San Francisco, CA, 2012.
38. M. Jensen, C. Meyer, J. Somorovsky, and J. Schwenk, "On the Effectiveness of XML Schema Validation for Countering XML Signature Wrapping Attacks," First International Workshop on Securing Services on the Cloud, Milan, Italy, September 2011.
39. S. Gajek, M. Jensen, L. Liao, and J. Schwenk, "Analysis of Signature Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, pp. 575–582, Miami, Florida, July 2009.

Data Mining Model Performance Of Sales Predictive Algorithms Based On Rapidminer Workflows

Alessandro Massaro, Vincenzo Maritati, Angelo Galiano

**Dyrecta Lab, IT research Laboratory, via Vescovo Simplicio,
45, 70014 Conversano (BA), Italy**

ABSTRACT

By applying RapidMiner workflows has been processed a dataset originated from different data files, and containing information about the sales over three years of a large chain of retail stores. Subsequently, has been constructed a Deep Learning model performing a predictive algorithm suitable for sales forecasting. This model is based on artificial neural network –ANN- algorithm able to learn the model starting from sales historical data and by pre-processing the data. The best built model uses a multilayer eural network together with an “optimized operator” able to find automatically the best parameter setting of the implemented algorithm. In order to prove the best performing predictive model, other machine learning algorithms have been tested. The performance comparison has been performed between Support Vector Machine –SVM-, k-Nearest Neighbor k-NN-, Gradient Boosted Trees, Decision Trees, and Deep Learning algorithms. The comparison of the degree of correlation between real and predicted values, the verage absolute error and the relative average error proved that ANN exhibited the best performance. The Gradient Boosted Trees approach represents an alternative approach having the second best performance. The case of study has been developed within the framework of an industry project oriented on the integration of high performance data mining models able to predict sales using–ERP- and customer relationship management –CRM- tools.

KEYWORDS

RapidMiner, Neural Network, Deep Learning, Gradient Boosted Trees, Data Mining Performance, Sales Prediction.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijsit/V10N3/10318ijsit03.pdf>

Volume Link: http://aircse.org/journal/ijsit2018_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Penpece D., & Elma O. E. (2014) "[Predicting Sales Revenue by Using Artificial Neural Network in Grocery Retailing Industry: A Case Study in Turkey](#)", International Journal of Trade Economics and Finance, Vol. 5, No. 5, pp435-440.
- [2] Thiesing F. M., & Vornberger, O. (1997) "[Sales Forecasting Using Neural Networks](#)", IEEE Proceedings ICNN'97, Houston, Texas, 9-12 June 1997, pp2125-2128.
- [3] Zhang, G. P. (2003) "[Time series forecasting using a hybrid ARIMA and neural network model](#)", Neurocomputing, Vol. 50, pp159-175.
- [4] Sharma, A., & Panigrahi, P. K. (2011) "[Neural Network based Approach for Predicting Customer Churn in Cellular Network Services](#)", International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 27, No.11, pp0975-8887.
- [5] Kamakura, W., Mela, C. F., Ansari A., & al. (2005) "[Choice Models and Customer Relationship Management](#)", Marketing Letters, Vol. 16, No.3/4, pp279-291.
- [6] Smith, K. A., & Gupta, J. N. D. (2000) "[Neural Networks in Business: Techniques and Applications for the Operations Researcher](#)", Computers & Operations Research, Vol. 27, No. 11-12, pp1023- 1044.
- [7] Chattopadhyay, M., Dan, P. K., Majumdar, S., & Chakraborty, P. S. (2012) "[Application of Artificial Neural Network in Market Segmentation: A Review on Recent Trends](#)", Management Science Letters, Vol. 2, pp425-438.
- [8] Berry, J. A. M., & Linoff, G. S. (2004) "[Data Mining Techniques For Marketing, Sales, and Customer Relationship Management](#)", Wiley, Second Edition.
- [9] Buttle, F. (2009) "[Customer Relationship Management Concepts and Technologies](#)", Elsevier, Second Edition.
- [10] Thomassey, S. (2014) "[Sales Forecasting in Apparel and Fashion Industry: A Review](#)", Springer, chapter 2.
- [11] Massaro, A. Barbuzzi, D., Vitti, V., Galiano, A., Aruci, M., Pirlo, G. (2016) "[Predictive Sales Analysis According to the Effect of Weather](#)", Proceeding of the 2nd International Conference on Recent Trends and Applications in Computer Science and Information Technology, Tirana, Albania, November 18 - 19, pp53-55.
- [12] Parsons, A.G. (2001), "[The Association between Daily Weather and Daily Shopping Patterns](#)", Australasian Marketing Journal, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp78-84.
- [13] Steele, A.T., (1951) "Weather's Effect on the Sales of a Department Store", Journal of Marketing Vol. 15, No. 4, pp436-443.
- [14] Murray, K. B., Di Muro, F., Finn, A., & Leszczyc, P. P. (2010) "[The Effect of Weather on Consumer Spending](#)", Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, Vol. 17, No.6, pp512-520.

- [15] Massaro, A., Galiano, A., Barbuzzi, D., Pellicani, L., Birardi, G., Romagno, D. D., & Frulli, L., (2017) "[Joint Activities of Market Basket Analysis and Product Facing for Business Intelligence oriented on Global Distribution Market: examples of data mining applications](#)," International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, Vol. 8, No.2 , pp178-183.
- [16] Aguinis, H., Forcum, L. E., & Joo, H. (2013) "[Using Market Basket Analysis in Management Research](#)," Journal of Management, Vol. 39, No. 7, pp1799-1824.
- [17] Štulec, I, Petljak, K., & Kukor, A. (2016) "[The Role of Store Layout and Visual Merchandising in Food Retailing](#)", European Journal of Economics and Business Studies, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp139-152.
- [18] Otha, M. & Higuci, Y. (2013) "Study on Design of Supermarket Store Layouts: the Principle of "Sales Magnet"", World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 7, No. 1, pp209-212.
- [19] Shallu, & Gupta, S. (2013) "[Impact of Promotional Activities on Consumer Buying Behavior: A Study of Cosmetic Industry](#)", International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management (IJCBM), Vol. 2, No.6, pp379-385.
- [20] Al Essa, A. & Bach, C. (2014)" [Data Mining and Knowledge Management for Marketing](#)", International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp321-328.
- [21] Kotu, V., & Deshpande B. (2015) "Predictive Analytics and Data Mining- Concepts and Practice with RapidMiner" Elsevier.
- [22] Wimmer, H., Powell, L. M. (2015) "[A Comparison of Open Source Tools for Data Science](#)", Proceedings of the Conference on Information Systems Applied Research. Wilmington, North Carolina USA.
- [23] Al-Khoder, A., Harmouch, H., "[Evaluating Four Of The most Popular Open Source and Free Data Mining Tools](#)", International Journal of Academic Scientific Research, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp13-23.
- [24] Gulli, A., & Pal, S. (2017) "Deep Learning with Keras- Implement neural networks with Keras on Theano and TensorFlow," Birmingham -Mumbai Packt book, ISBN 978-1-78712-842-2.
- [25] Kovalev, V., Kalinovsky, A., & Kovalev, S. (2016) "[Deep Learning with Theano, Torch, Caffe, TensorFlow, and deeplearning4j: which one is the best in speed and accuracy?](#)" Proceeding of XIII Int. Conf. on Pattern Recognition and Information Processing, 3-5 October, Minsk, Belarus State University, pp99-103.

AUTHOR

Alessandro Massaro: Research & Development Chief of Dyrecta Lab s.r.l.

CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK BASED FEATURE EXTRACTION FOR IRIS RECOGNITION

Maram.G Alaslani¹ and Lamiaa A. Elrefaei^{1,2}

¹Computer Science Department, Faculty of Computing and Information
Technology, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

²Electrical Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering at Shoubra, Benha
University, Cairo, Egypt

ABSTRACT

Iris is a powerful tool for reliable human identification. It has the potential to identify individuals with a high degree of assurance. Extracting good features is the most significant step in the iris recognition system. In the past, different features have been used to implement iris recognition system. Most of them are depend on hand-crafted features designed by biometrics specialists. Due to the success of deep learning in computer vision problems, the features learned by the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) have gained much attention to be applied for iris recognition system. In this paper, we evaluate the extracted learned features from a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (Alex-Net Model) followed by a multi-class Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm to perform classification. The performance of the proposed system is investigated when extracting features from the segmented iris image and from the normalized iris image. The proposed iris recognition system is tested on four public datasets IITD, iris databases CASIAIris-V1, CASIA-Iris-thousand and, CASIA-Iris- V3 Interval. The system achieved excellent results with the very high accuracy rate.

KEYWORDS

Biometrics, Iris, Recognition, Deep learning, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Feature extraction (FE).

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V10N2/10218ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link: http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2018_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Haghghat, S. Zonouz, and M. Abdel-Mottaleb, "CloudID: Trustworthy cloud-based and crossenterprise biometric identification," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 42, pp. 7905-7916, 2015.
- [2] D. Kesavaraja, D. Sasireka, and D. Jeyabharathi, "[Cloud software as a service with iris authentication](#)," *Journal of Global Research in Computer Science*, vol. 1, pp. 16-22, 2010.
- [3] N. Shah and P. Shrinath, "Iris Recognition System–A Review," *International Journal of Computer and Information Technology*, vol. 3, 2014.
- [4] A. B. Dehkordi and S. A. Abu-Bakar, "[A review of iris recognition system](#)," *Jurnal Teknologi*, vol. 77, 2015.
- [5] S. Minaee, A. Abdolrashidiy, and Y. Wang, "[An experimental study of deep convolutional features for iris recognition](#)," in *Signal Processing in Medicine and Biology Symposium (SPMB)*, 2016 IEEE, 2016, pp. 1-6. *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT) Vol 10, No 2, April 2018 77*
- [6] S. Minaee, A. Abdolrashidi, and Y. Wang, "Iris recognition using scattering transform and textural features," in *Signal Processing and Signal Processing Education Workshop (SP/SPE)*, 2015 IEEE, 2015, pp. 37-42.
- [7] S. Minaee, A. Abdolrashidi, and Y. Wang, "[Face Recognition Using Scattering Convolutional Network](#)," arXiv preprint arXiv:1608.00059, 2016.
- [8] IIT Delhi Database. Available: <http://www4.comp.polyu.edu.hk/~csajaykr/IITD/Database Iris.htm>. Accessed 14 April 2017.
- [9] (2 April 2017). CASIA Iris Image Database Version 1.0. Available: <http://www.idealtest.org/findDownloadDbByMode.do?mode=Iris>. Accessed 12 April 2017.
- [10] CASIA Iris Image Database Version 4.0 (CAS IA-Iris-Thousand). Available: <http://biometrics.idealtest.org/dbDetailForUser.do?id=4>. Accessed 17 April 2017.
- [11] CASIA Iris Image Database Version 3.0 (CASIA-Iris-Interval). Available: <http://biometrics.idealtest.org/dbDetailForUser.do?id=3>. Accessed 17 April 2017.
- [12] K. Nguyen, C. Fookes, A. Ross, and S. Sridharan, "Iris Recognition with Off-the-Shelf CNN Features: A Deep Learning Perspective," *IEEE Access*, 2017.
- [13] A. Romero, C. Gatta, and G. Camps-Valls, "Unsupervised deep feature extraction for remote sensing image classification," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 54, pp. 1349-1362, 2016.

- [14] O. Oyedotun and A. Khashman, "[Iris nevus diagnosis: convolutional neural network and deep belief network](#)," Turkish Journal of Electrical Engineering & Computer Sciences, vol. 25, pp. 1106-1115, 2017.
- [15] A. S. Al-Waisy, R. Qahwaji, S. Ipson, S. Al-Fahdawi, and T. A. Nagem, "[A multi-biometric iris recognition system based on a deep learning approach](#)," Pattern Analysis and Applications, pp. 1-20, 2017.
- [16] J. Nagi, F. Ducatelle, G. A. Di Caro, D. Cireşan, U. Meier, A. Giusti, F. Nagi, J. Schmidhuber, and L. M. Gambardella, "[Max-pooling convolutional neural networks for vision-based hand gesture recognition](#)," in Signal and Image Processing Applications (ICSIPA), 2011 IEEE International Conference on, 2011, pp. 342-347.
- [17] D. Scherer, A. Müller, and S. Behnke, "[Evaluation of pooling operations in convolutional architectures for object recognition](#)," Artificial Neural Networks–ICANN 2010, pp. 92-101, 2010.
- [18] J. van Doorn, "[Analysis of deep convolutional neural network architectures](#)," 2014.
- [19] C. L. Lam and M. Eizenman, "[Convolutional neural networks for eye detection in remote gaze estimation systems](#)," 2008.
- [20] S. Ahmad Radzi, K.-H. Mohamad, S. S. Liew, and R. Bakhteri, "[Convolutional neural network for face recognition with pose and illumination variation](#)," International Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJET), vol. 6, pp. 44-57, 2014.
- [21] K. Itqan, A. Syafeeza, F. Gong, N. Mustafa, Y. Wong, and M. Ibrahim, "[User identification system based on finger-vein patterns using Convolutional Neural Network](#)," ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, vol. 11, pp. 3316-3319, 2016.
- [22] S. Sangwan and R. Rani, "[A Review on: Iris Recognition](#)," (IJCSIT) International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, vol. 6, pp. 3871-3873, 2015
- [23] C. Jayachandra and H. V. Reddy, "[Iris Recognition based on Pupil using Canny edge detection and KMeans Algorithm](#)," Int. J. Eng. Comput. Sci., vol. 2, pp. 221-225, 2013.
- [24] L. A. Elrefaei, D. H. Hamid, A. A. Bayazed, S. S. Bushnak, and S. Y. Maasher, "[Developing Iris Recognition System for Smartphone Security](#)," Multimedia Tools and Applications, pp. 1-25, 2017.
- [25] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton, "[Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks](#)," in Advances in neural information processing systems, 2012, pp. 1097-1105.
- [26] S. Minaee and Y. Wang, "[Palmprint Recognition Using Deep Scattering Convolutional Network](#)," arXiv preprint arXiv:1603.09027, 2016.

- [27] J. Weston and C. Watkins, "[Multi-class support vector machines](#)," Technical Report CSD-TR-98-04, Department of Computer Science, Royal Holloway, University of London, May 1998.
- [28] G. Xu, Z. Zhang, and Y. Ma, "[A novel method for iris feature extraction based on intersecting cortical model network](#)," Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computing, vol. 26, pp. 341-352, 2008.
- [29] M. Abhiram, C. Sadhu, K. Manikantan, and S. Ramachandran, "[Novel DCT based feature extraction for enhanced iris recognition](#)," in Communication, Information & Computing Technology (ICCICT), 2012 International Conference on, 2012, pp. 1-6.
- [30] M. Elgamal and N. Al-Biqami, "[An efficient feature extraction method for iris recognition based on wavelet transformation](#)," Int. J. Comput. Inf. Technol, vol. 2, pp. 521-527, 2013.
- [31] B. Bharath, A. Vilas, K. Manikantan, and S. Ramachandran, "[Iris recognition using radon transform thresholding based feature extraction with Gradient-based Isolation as a pre-processing technique](#)," in Industrial and Information Systems (ICIIS), 2014 9th International Conference on, 2014, pp. 1-8.
- [32] S. S. Dhage, S. S. Hegde, K. Manikantan, and S. Ramachandran, "[DWT-based feature extraction and radon transform based contrast enhancement for improved iris recognition](#)," Procedia Computer Science, vol. 45, pp. 256-265, 2015.

AUTHORS

Maram G. Alaslani Received her B.Sc. degree in Computer Science with Honors from King Abdulaziz University in 2010. She works as Teaching Assistant from 2011 to date at Faculty of Computers and Information Technology at King Abdulaziz University, Rabigh, Saudi Arabia. Now she is working in her Master Degree at King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. She has a research interest in image processing, pattern recognition, and neural network.

Lamiaa A. Elrefaei received her B.Sc. degree with honors in Electrical Engineering (Electronics and Telecommunications) in 1997, her M.Sc. in 2003 and Ph.D. in 2008 in Electrical Engineering (Electronics) from faculty of Engineering at Shoubra, Benha University, Egypt. She held a number of faculty positions at Benha University, as Teaching Assistant from 1998 to 2003, as an Assistant Lecturer from 2003 to 2008, and has been a lecturer from 2008 to date. She is currently an Associate Professor at the faculty of Computing and Information Technology, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. Her research interests include computational intelligence, biometrics, multimedia security, wireless networks, and Nano networks. She is a senior member of IEEE.